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Youth and aging in the tissue stem cell.

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We measured total transcription with microarray sequencing technology in the hair follicle stem cell (HFSC/IFE) in young mice, at 12 weeks, and in old age, at 25 months, for discovery of factors necessary or important for rejuvenation, youth or aging in mammals.

Results

We studied the hair follicle stem cell in youth and in old age in mice to identify novel factors necessary for maintenance or rejuvenation of youth in mammals.

1. Chemokines
 - i. Ccl20
2. Vomeronasal system
 - i. Vmn1r229
3. Olfactory system
 - i. Olfr902
 - ii. Olfr1161
4. Interferon system
 - i. Ifi203
5. Cell adhesion
 - i. Pcdhb5
6. DNA Damage
 - i. Ddr2
7. Ras pathway
 - i. Rassf2
8. Cell surface
 - i. Ttc29
 - ii. Fam184b
 - iii. Lrriq3
 - iv. Fam3b
9. Immune receptor
 - i. Skint5
 - ii. Skint10
 - iii. Icos
10. Other immune
 - i. Xlr5c
 - ii. Irf8
11. Zinc finger nuclear protein
 - i. Zfp317
 - ii. Zfp800
12. Fatty acid, lipid and cholesterol
 - i. Ch25h
 - ii. Fads6
13. Other
 - i. Rp1
 - ii. Slc35d3
 - iii. Spata9
 - iv. Izumo3
 - v. Lmod3
 - vi. Prokr2
14. Unannotated
 - i. Gm4583
 - ii. 9430031I16Rik
 - iii. AI480526
 - iv. I830077J02Rik
 - v. 2410137F16Rik
 - vi. 9330199F22Rik
 - vii. Gm7715
 - viii. Loc674392
 - ix. BC055004
 - x. AU045094
 - xi. A630038E17Rik
 - xii. 1700065I16Rik

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15. Depleted, absent, silenced or lost in youth

- i. Sdpr
- ii. 8430406I07Rik
- iii. Mras
- iv. Prdx4
- v. B020031H02Rik